

IMPROVEMENT OF THE AXIAL BUCKLING CAPACITY OF COMPOSITE ELLIPTICAL CYLINDRICAL SHELLS

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SUMMARY

To mitigate the reduced axial buckling capacity of a noncircular cylindrical shell relative to the buckling capacity of a circular cylindrical shell of the same circumference, wall thickness, length, and therefore the same weight, the fiber orientation is varied with circumferential position. Substantial gains in performance are computed.

Keywords: material tailoring, fiber angle tailoring, collapse, material failure

INTRODUCTION

Because of their efficiency, cylindrical structures have been used for many applications. The cross sections of the vast majority of cylindrical structures are circular, but there could be applications where a noncircular cross section may be more suitable. Aircraft fuselages for blended wing body designs and tankage within geometrically constrained volumes are but two examples where a noncircular construction may offer distinct advantages. However, the overall effect of the noncircular cross section is a degradation in the axial buckling capacity compared to a circular cylinder of the same circumference, wall thickness, and length. This situation is illustrated in Fig. 1 for a simply-supported fiber-reinforced composite cylinder with an elliptical cross section and a quasi-isotropic lamination sequence, where only the flatter portions of the cross section participate in the buckling deformations. The axial buckling load for this cylinder is 30-40% less than the axial buckling load of a quasi-isotropic circular cylinder with the same circumference. Similar characteristics are exhibited for cylinders constructed of other lamination sequences and

Fig. 1 – Axial buckling deformations of a simply-supported quasi-isotropic elliptical cylinder

Similar characteristics are exhibited for cylinders constructed of other lamination sequences and

of isotropic materials. The decreased buckling performance is due to the large radius of curvature associated with the flatter portions of the cross section. The decreased performance can also be viewed as being due to an inefficient or ineffective use of material in the more highly curved portions of the cross section. It would seem that the material properties of the cylinder could be tailored to involve the entire cylinder in the buckling phenomenon, thereby increasing the axial buckling capacity. Since the radius of curvature varies in a continuous fashion with the circumferential coordinate, it is logical that the material properties, particularly the stiffness, should also vary continuously with the circumferential coordinate. This is the approach summarized in this paper.

APPROACH

The $[\pm 45/0/90]_S$ quasi-isotropic elliptical cylindrical shell of Fig. 1 is considered the baseline case. To improve the axial buckling capacity, a $(\pm\theta/0/90)_S$ laminate is selected for the cylinder wall, where θ is varied with circumferential location. Of course for $\theta = 45$ deg. the laminate is the quasi-isotropic baseline case. The variation of θ with circumferential position will be determined by requiring the axial buckling strain at each circumferential position to be the same. That the axial strain would be the same can be expected, as a cylinder would typically terminate with circumferential stiffeners or bulkheads which would enforce the same axial kinematics at all circumferential locations. However, that this strain would be the axial buckling strain would depend on the local radius of curvature and the local axial and circumferential stiffness properties. Here it is hypothesized that by considering $(\pm\theta/0/90)_S$ circular cylinders with θ the same at all circumferential locations and considering radii in the range $R_{\min} \leq R \leq R_{\max}$, where R_{\min} and R_{\max} are the minimum and maximum radii of curvature of the ellipse of interest, the manner by which to tailor the local radius of curvature and local the fiber angle θ , and therefore the local stiffnesses of the $(\pm\theta/0/90)_S$, can be determined.

To understand the influences of the radius of curvature R and fiber angle θ , an approximate approach is used to compute the buckling strains of circular cylinders as a function of those two parameters. The approximate approach assumes an applied circumferentially uniform axial displacement, a membrane prebuckling state, simple-support boundary conditions, and a harmonic variation with the axial and circumferential coordinates of the buckling deformations. Clamped conditions are considered, but the results will only be briefly mentioned. To focus on specific cylinders, the geometry and material properties listed in Table 1 are used, where conventional nomenclature is used for the material properties. Two cylinder geometries, herein referred to as small and large cylinders, are considered. As can be seen, only one aspect ratio, here defined as the ratio of the minor radius b to major radius a is considered, namely 0.70. The dimensions and material properties of the cylinders considered are similar to those used in past work. [1, 2]. Only the results for the small cylinder case will be presented here, while, again, results for the large cylinder will only be briefly mentioned. Based on a finite-element analysis to be discussed later, for the

baseline quasi-isotropic elliptical cylinder with the properties of Table 1, the buckling, or critical, axial displacement, strain, and load listed in Table 2 are computed.

Results from this approximate analysis are summarized in Fig. 2, where the horizontal axis is the radius of the circular cylinder, normalized by R_{max} , and the vertical axis is the layer angle θ in the laminate stacking sequence $[\pm\theta/0/90]_S$. Contours of buckling strain of circular cylinders are normalized by the buckling strain of the baseline quasi-isotropic elliptical cylinder of Fig. 1 and Tables 1 and 2. A

number of interesting points can be made from Fig. 2. Point A, for example, represents the fact that for a circular cylinder with normalized radius of 0.5 and fiber angle θ of 18 deg., i.e., a circular cylinder constructed entirely of laminate $[\pm 18/0/90]_S$, the normalized buckling strain is 0.75. Likewise, point B represents the fact that for a circular cylinder with normalized radius of 0.9, a larger cylinder, and a fiber angle θ of 33 deg., the normalized buckling strain is also 0.75. Interestingly, because the contour line for a normalized strain of 0.75 has two branches, point B' represents the fact that the buckling strain for a cylinder with a normalized radius of 0.9, but a fiber angle θ of 83 deg., is also 0.75. This branch of larger angles will be referred to as the conjugate branch. To be noted is the fact that there are conjugate branches for some buckling strain levels and not others, and some buckling strain levels are valid only over a limited range of normalized radii. Also to be noted is that the normalized buckling strain of a quasi-isotropic circular cylinder with a maximum radius of curvature is unity, point C on the figure, where $\theta = 45$ deg. Since the normalization factor is the buckling strain of the quasi-isotropic elliptical cylinder, this is interpreted to mean that the buckling strain of the quasi-isotropic elliptical cylinder is equal to the buckling strain of a quasi-isotropic circular cylinder

Property (units)	Numerical Value	
	small cylinder	large cylinder
Major radius, a (m)	0.1250	0.625
Minor radius, b (m)	0.0875	0.438
Length, L (m)	0.320	1.600
R_{min} (m)	0.0613	0.307
R_{max} (m)	0.1786	0.890
R_0 (m)*	0.1070	0.535
wall thickness, H , (mm)	$8h = 1.120$	$16h = 2.24$
E_1 (GPa)	130.0	
E_2 (GPa)	9.70	
G_{12} (GPa)	5.00	
ν_{12}	0.300	
layer thickness, h (mm)	0.1400	

* R_0 = radius of circular cylinder with same circumference

Laminate	Δ_{cr} (mm)	$\epsilon_{cr}(10^{-3})$	P_{cr} (kN)
$[\pm 45/0/90]_S$	1.110	3.47	130.5

* based on dimensions and material properties of small cylinder in Table 1

Fig. 2 - Buckling strain contours as a function of radius R for simply-supported circular cylinders with lamination sequence $[\pm\theta/0/90]_s$ based on a simplified buckling analysis

with a radius $R = R_{max}$ of the elliptical cylinder. This correlates well with the established relation for the so-called buckling stress of an isotropic elliptical cylinder given as [3]

$$\sigma_{cr} = \frac{EH}{R_{max} \sqrt{3(1-\nu^2)}} \quad (1)$$

The fact that the quasi-isotropic elliptical composite cylinder of Fig. 1 buckles only in the flatter portions of the cross section, where $R = R_{max}$, also supports this relation.

To follow a particular strain contour over the range from R_{min} to R_{max} in Fig. 2 provides guidance for how to vary the fiber angle θ in the lamination sequence $[\pm\theta/0/90]_s$ as a function of radius of curvature for an elliptical cylinder. And since the radius of curvature and the circumferential location for an elliptical cross section can be related by geometry, the fiber angle θ as function of circumferential location can be specified so that the entire elliptical cylinder buckles at this particular level of axial strain.

If Fig. 2 is any sort of guide, several material tailoring schemes have essentially been prescribed which would lead to the entire cylinder participating in the buckling deformations at the critical level of axial displacement. Specifically, consider the

normalized buckling strain level of 1.152. This level is close to the normalized buckling strain level of 1.0 for the quasi-isotropic elliptical cylinder in Fig. 1, and it is the maximum buckling strain level that can be achieved over the entire range of radii R_{min} to R_{max} , i.e., the contour for 1.152 starts at the boundary $R = R_{min}$ and is just tangent to the boundary $R = R_{max}$. Using this contour, at the sides of the cylinder, i.e., at R_{min} , the fiber angle should be $\theta = 19$ deg. and at the crown and keel, i.e., at R_{max} , the fiber angle should be $\theta = 62$ deg.

Another tailoring scheme of interest is the one associated with the conjugate branch for normalized strain level 1.152. For this branch, which represents the so-called tailored-conjugate cylinder, the fiber angles in the lamination sequence $[\pm\theta/0/90]_s$ are not a continuous function of circumferential location. Moving from the crown and keel regions toward the side regions on the conjugate branch requires that at R/R_{max} approx 0.53 the fiber angle θ suddenly change to that prescribed by the primary branch, a value of approximately 38 deg. So, to some extent, this case is not totally practical.

A third tailoring scheme of interest is the one associated with the normalized buckling strain of 1.0. For this case, at the crown and keel of the cylinder the fiber angle is 45 deg. This tailoring scheme will be referred to as the quasi-isotropic crown case. For this case the strain level of the tailored cylinder is the same as the strain level in the baseline quasi-isotropic cylinder, and in the crown and keel regions the lamination sequence is a familiar one, namely quasi-isotropic.

BUCKLING PERFORMANCE OF TAILORED DESIGNS

In order to determine if tailoring the fiber angle circumferentially based on Fig. 2, or the counterpart figure for the large simply-supported cylinder, results in better buckling performance, a geometrically nonlinear finite-element analysis of each the three tailoring schemes, i.e., tailored, tailored-conjugate, and quasi-isotropic crown, was conducted using the commercially-available finite-element code ABAQUS. The results presented here are based on modeling the cylinders with 80 elements in the axial direction and 168 elements in the circumferential direction, for a total of 13,440 elements. Models with 160 elements in the axial direction and 336 in the circumferential direction, for a total of 53,760 elements, were used to check convergence characteristics. The elements were four-node S4R elements with six degrees-of-freedom per node. For the purpose of varying the fiber angle with circumferential position, each quadrant of the elliptical cross section was divided into 14 equal-circumferential-length regions. With 168 elements in the circumferential direction, each quadrant consisted of 42 elements, and hence each of the 14 regions contained three finite elements. Within each region the lamination sequence was $[\pm\theta/0/90]_s$ with θ fixed. The particular value of θ for each region, and hence for the three elements in the region, was taken from the R/R_{max} vs. θ relation of Fig. 2 for each particular tailoring scheme by using the average radius for each equal-length region to select the value of θ . For the finite-element model this was translated to fiber angle as a function of circumferential location. Of interest for each tailoring scheme were the buckling load, the buckling mode shapes, and the collapsed load level. Regarding the latter, when the design of a structural component is tailored to exhibit improved performance for a particular condition or

response, often other responses suffer. For this problem, since the tailored designs for improved buckling load have been derived from a strain-, or displacement-, based perspective, another important measure of performance is the axial load associated with the collapsed state of the cylinder at the same overall axial displacement level. Hence, a variety of analysis options in the finite-element code were used. Specifically, geometrically nonlinear static analyses were used to study the prebuckling behavior of the cylinders to the axial compressive displacement, and to determine the onset of instability, which was assumed to occur when the level of axial displacement was such that the tangent stiffness matrix of the finite-element model was singular. Eigenvalue analyses based on a geometrically nonlinear prebuckling state were also used to study the onset of instability. These two approaches predicted nearly identical axial displacements for the onset of instability. Transient dynamic analyses were initiated at the onset of instability to determine the collapsed state of the cylinders. To provide a further comparison for the tailored designs, elliptical cylinders with lamination sequences $[\pm 19/0/90]_S$ and $[\pm 62/0/90]_S$, uniform with circumference, were considered. These two cases were considered because these laminates are at the extremes of the range of fiber angles for the 1.152 normalized strain level in Fig. 2 and it is plausible that they could out-perform that tailored case.

Small Cylinders

The buckling strains and buckling loads for the various lamination sequences investigated are summarized in Table 3. The collapse loads, to be discussed later, are

Laminate	Normalized Buckling Strain or Displacement ¹	Normalized Buckling Load ²	Normalized Collapsed Load ²
quasi-isotropic $[\pm 45/0/90]_S$	1	1	0.596
tailored	1.056	1.279	0.464
tailored-conjugate	1.094	1.183	0.460
quasi-isotropic-crown	0.977	1.297	0.450
$[\pm 19/0/90]_S$	0.451	0.783	0.512
$[\pm 62/0/90]_S$	1.111	0.915	0.589

¹ normalized by the buckling strain and displacement for the $[\pm 45/0/90]_S$ case in Table 2
² normalized by the buckling load for the $[\pm 45/0/90]_S$ case in Table 2

also listed. The results have been normalized by the counterpart buckling values for the baseline quasi-isotropic elliptical cylinder cited earlier. Immediately obvious is that fact that all tailored designs result in increased buckling loads relative to the quasi-isotropic elliptical case. The tailored design using a normalized strain level of 1.152 results in nearly a 28% increase in buckling load, the tailored-conjugate design 18%, and the quasi-isotropic crown design, which is based on a normalized buckling strain level of 1.0, nearly 30%. The fact the quasi-isotropic-crown cylinder exhibits more load capacity

improvement relative to the quasi-isotropic cylinder, while being subjected to less axial compression strain than the tailored cylinder, is because the overall axial stiffness for the quasi-isotropic-crown cylinder is greater than that of the tailored cylinder. Overall, the fibers are more aligned with the axial direction for the quasi-isotropic crown case than for the tailored or tailored-conjugate designs. As a result, the axial load (strain multiplied by overall axial stiffness) for the quasi-isotropic crown design is greater than that for the case of tailored design. To be noted is that the buckling loads for the $[\pm 19/0/90]_s$ and $[\pm 62/0/90]_s$ cylinders are about 20% and 10% less than the baseline case, respectively. It should also be noted that because the axial strain is simply the axial displacement divided by the cylinder length, normalized values of buckling axial displacement, though not shown, would be identical to the normalized values of the axial strain.

The buckling mode shapes for the various cases are illustrated in Fig. 3, including for comparison the buckling mode shape of a quasi-isotropic circular cylinder with the equivalent radius of curvature R_o (see Table 1). What is immediately obvious from Fig. 3 is that buckling deformations of the three tailored designs, Figs. 3a, b, and c, encompass the entire cylinder, not just the crown and keel regions, as is the case for the equivalent quasi-isotropic circular cylinder shown in Fig. 3d. The deformations of the tailored cylinder, Fig. 3a, form a short wavelength double-sinusoidal-like pattern in the axial and circumferential directions in the crown and keel regions, which transition into a more spiral-like pattern in the side regions. Those characteristics aside, the crown, keel, and side regions all participate in the buckling deformations. For the tailored-conjugate and quasi-isotropic-crown cylinders, Figs. 3b and c, respectively, spiral-like deformation patterns encompass all circumferential locations. The buckling deformations of the quasi-isotropic crown case show a strong resemblance to the buckling deformations of the equivalent quasi-isotropic circular cylinder, Fig. 3d. It should be mentioned that the buckling deformations for the $[\pm 19/0/90]_s$ and $[\pm 62/0/90]_s$ cylinders (not shown) are confined to the crown and keel regions. Tailoring the lamination sequence so the entire cylinder is involved in the buckling process appears to be tantamount to increasing the buckling load. It is remarkable that the guidelines for tailoring derived from Fig. 2 are as good as they are. The normalized buckling strain levels for the three tailored elliptical cylinders computed using the above-described many-degree-of-freedom geometrically nonlinear finite-element model coincide very closely with the two normalized buckling strain levels selected from Fig. 2, which are based on a simplified analysis of circular cylinders. Specifically, the variation in fiber orientation for the tailored and tailored-conjugate cylinders was based on a normalized buckling strain of 1.152 and on a normalized buckling strain of 1.0 for the quasi-isotropic-crown cylinder. The finite-element results predicted the tailored, tailored-conjugate, and quasi-isotropic crown designs would have buckling strains of 1.056, 1.094, and 0.977, respectively. These numbers represent less than a 10% difference between the buckling strains selected from the simplified analysis of Fig. 2 and the buckling strain levels actually computed by the more refined finite-element analysis. It is clear the results in Fig. 2 can be used to address the negative effects of the noncircular geometry in a very fundamental way.

a - tailored cylinder

b - tailored-conjugate cylinder

c - quasi-isotropic crown cylinder

d - quasi-isotropic circular cylinder

Fig. 3 – Axial buckling mode shapes for (a) tailored cylinder, (b) tailored-conjugate cylinder, (c) quasi-isotropic crown cylinder, (d) quasi-isotropic circular cylinder

Large Cylinders

For the large cylinder geometry of Table 1 the approximate analysis of simply-supported circular cylinders resulted in a figure very similar to Fig. 2. Tailored, tailored-conjugate, and quasi-isotropic crown designs were selected, as well as constant-angle cylinders representing the extreme angles 18 deg. and 56 deg. associated with the tailored design. Finite-element analyses of these three tailored designs for the large simply supported cylinders resulted in gains in axial buckling load about 5-10% greater than for each of the three tailored designs of the small cylinder. As with the small

cylinders, the buckling loads of the elliptical cylinders with the two extreme angle cases were smaller than for the quasi-isotropic elliptical cylinder.

Clamped Boundary Conditions

When the three tailored designs based on Fig. 2 were applied to elliptical cylinders with clamped boundary conditions, similar gains in performance were computed by the finite-element analyses. This perhaps could be expected because for the cylinder geometries considered, particularly the length and cross-sectional dimension combinations, the boundary conditions do not have a large influence on the buckling load.

Collapse Loads

As seen from Table 3, the collapse loads of the tailored small simply-supported cylinders are somewhat less than 50% of the buckling loads, as compared to 60% for the baseline quasi-isotropic case. The two extreme constant angle cases also have collapse loads greater than the tailored designs. Because of space limitations, material failure has not been discussed. However, suffice it to say that based on the predictions of the maximum stress failure criterion and reasonable values of failure stress levels, there are no fiber failures predicted for any of the three tailored designs in the collapsed state. For the quasi-isotropic baseline case fiber failure is predicted in the collapsed state. For all cases, failure due to excess intralaminar stresses perpendicular to the fibers is predicted. Hence the tailored designs offer the advantage of no fiber failure in the collapse state.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The concept of varying lamination fiber angle with circumferential location to off-set the degradation of axial buckling load of elliptical composite cylinders due to the varying radius of curvature appears to have merit. With the approach taken here, several designs for the variation of fiber angle with circumferential location were presented, each one showing some gain in the axial buckling load. The concept appears to be independent of cylinder size, and the tailored designs based on simply-support cylinders show similar improvements in axial buckling load when applied to the case of clamped boundary conditions. Though elliptical cross sections are a specific form of a noncircular geometry, and the dimensions of the elliptical cylinders considered here were even more specific, there is reason to believe the concept can be extended to other noncircular cross-sectional geometries, e.g., oval. Furthermore, variation of the lamination fiber angle for other loading conditions may produce gains in performance. Further discussion of the problem presented here is available in ref. 4

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